

Priprava podatkov in dokumentacije za digitalno skrbništvo

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Delavnica Ravnanje z raziskovalnimi podatki in odprti dostop

Katere stvari moram hraniti in kako

- podatki
- dokumentacija

Katera orodja so mi pri tem v pomoč

UK Data Service

FINNISH SOCIAL SCIENCE
DATA ARCHIVE

MANTRA

Research Data Management Training

IHSN

International Household Survey Network

DATA MANAGEMENT
GUIDELINES

Deljenje moje raziskave

Podatki morajo biti uporabnikom prijazni, morajo biti deljivi in dolgotrajno uporabni.

-> zagotoviti moramo, da bodo razumljivi vsakemu uporabniku

To seveda zahteva jasen opis podatkov, ustrezne kontekstualne informacije in dokumentacijo.

Lahko razumete / uporabite tovrstne podatke?

hec09ai.sav [DataSet2] - PASW Statistics Data Editor

File Edit View Data Transform Analyze Direct Marketing Graphs Utilities Add-ons Window Help

	Name	Type	Width	Decimals	Label	Values	Missing
175	quala10	Numeric	2	0	Which of the qualifications on this card do you have? 10	{-9, No ans...-99 - -1	
176	activb	Numeric	2	0	Activity status for last week	{-9, No ans...-99 - -1	
177	empstat	Numeric	2	0	Manager/Foreman	{-9, No ans...-99 - -1	
178	everjob	Numeric	2	0	Ever had paid employment or self-employed	{-9, No ans...-99 - -1	
179	ftptime	Numeric	2	0	Full-time or part-time	{-9, No ans...-99 - -1	
180	howlong	Numeric	2	0	How long have you been looking	{-9, No ans...-99 - -1	
181	wkstr2	Numeric	2	0	Able to start work within 2 weeks (Government training scheme)	{-9, No ans...-99 - -1	
182	wklook4	Numeric	2	0	Looking paid work/govt scheme last 4 weeks	{-9, No ans...-99 - -1	
183	nemplee	Numeric	2	0	Number employed at place of work	{-9, No ans...-99 - -1	
184	nssec	Numeric	5	1	NS-SEC - long version (harmonised)	{-9.0, No a...-99.0 - -1.0	
185	othpaid	Numeric	2	0	Ever had other employment (waiting to start work)	{-9, No ans...-99 - -1	
186	payage	Numeric	3	0	Age when last had a paid job	{-9, No ans...-99 - -1	
187	paylast	Numeric	4	0	Year left last paid job	{-9, No ans...-99 - -1	
188	paymon	Numeric	2	0	Month last left paid job	{-9, No ans...-99 - -1	
189	sclass	Numeric	2	0	Social Class	{-9, No ans...-99 - -1	
190	seg	Numeric	2	0	Socio-Economic Group	{-9, No ans...-99 - -1	
191	snemplee	Numeric	2	0	Self employed, how many employees	{-9, No ans...-99 - -1	
192	age	Numeric	3	0	Age last birthday	{-9, No ans...-99 - -1	

Data View Variable View

Kaj je potrebno hraniti?

Hranimo uporabno dokumentacijo, kot so:

- končna poročila, objavljena poročila, navodila za uporabnika, delovni dokumenti, publikacije, laboratorijski zapiski ...

Informacijo o podatkovni strukturi:

- popis podatkovnih datotek,
- informacijo o povezanih ali hierarhičnih datotekah,
- evidence, posamezne primere ...

Dokumentacijo na ravni spremenljivk:

- imena spremenljivk / okrajšave,
- posamezna kodiranja in klasifikacije,
- informacijo o manjkajočih vrednostih,
- odstopanja in združevanja.

DMP

↑
Začni z zbiranjem pomembnih informacija
čim zgodnje v raziskovalnem procesu.

Dokumentacija podatkovne datoteke

Določeni tipi podatkovni datotek lahko vsebujejo informacije, ki jih je potrebno ohraniti:

- poimenovanje spremenljivke / kategorije odgovorov; metapodatki dokumenta; povezanost med tabelami in poizvedbami v relacijskih datotekah, GIS podatkovne plasti / tabele.

Na primer:

- SPSS: lastnosti spremenljivk dokumentirani v t.i. „Variable View „(ime spremenljivke, koda, podatkovni tip, manjkajoče vrednosti),
- MS Access: povezanost med tabelami,
- ArcGIS: rastrske slike in drugi vektorski podatki,
- MS Excel: lastnosti dokumenta, poimenovanja delovnih listov (kadar je teh več).

Nadzor nad kakovostjo podatkov

Metoda zbiranja podatkov in uporabljen inštrument bosta v veliki meri vplivala na to, kako (če sploh) so podatki (in spremno gradivo) hranjeni v elektronski obliki.

V spletnih anketah se odgovori zapišejo v bazo takoj, ko so podani. V računalniško podprtem osebnem anketiranju ali telefonskih anketah anketar vnaša odgovore med samim intervjujem. Papirnatih vprašalnikov je moč prebrati z optičnimi bralniki ali pa so v program vneseni ročno. Vse metode zbiranja podatkov lahko povzročijo napake pri podatkih.

Nadzor nad kakovostjo podatkov

Kvaliteto podatkov lahko izboljšamo z naslednjimi pristopi:

- Preveri in popravi vrednosti izven dovoljenega območja.
- Vnesene podatke primerjaj z naključno izbranimi vprašalniki.
- Preveri dolžino vrstic in število spremenljivk.
- Ne preoblikuj spremenljivk (združevanje kategorij) med samim vnosom.
- Kadar se podatki vnašajo ročno, pazi na, da so varnostne kopije hranjene ločeno in dovolj pogosto.
- Pri preoblikovanju spremenljivk uporablaj statistična orodja in zapisuj spremembe z uporabo sintakse.
- Preveri veljavnost frekvenc.
- Pripravi in hrani dokumentacijo vseh sprememb, ki so bile narejene na datoteki.

Vir: [FSD: Data Management Guidelines](#)

Dokumentacija podatkovne datoteke: ime spremenljivk

Strukturirani/ tabelarični podatki morajo imeti ustrezno dokumentiran zapis spremenljivk (kratko ime, opis spremenljivke in opis vrednosti).

Kratko ime spremenljivke je lahko npr. :

- povezano z imenom in številko vprašanja v anketi

Q1a, Q1b, Q2, Q3a

- numerično številčenje

V1, V2, V3

- smiselna okrajšava vprašanja ali pomena spremenljivke

moocc=mother occupation, faocc=father occupation

star=starost anketiranca

lr=leto rojstva

Dokumentacija podatkovne datoteke: ime spremenljivk

- Za interoperabilnost med orodji (zagotavljanje dolgoročne hrambe) je ključno, da ime spremenljivke zasede do 8 znakov brez presledkov, prvi znak naj ne bo številka.
- Ne pozabimo ustrezno poimenovati dodatnih spremenljivk – okoljskih spremenljivk včasih ni v vprašalniku. Npr. velikost naselja (na podlagi vzorca).

Uporabimo poimenovanja bv1, bv2 (bv= background variable)

- V podatkovno datoteko se lahko doda tudi dodatne informacije, ki ne izhajajo neposredno iz raziskovalnega instrumenta – npr. datum zbiranja podatkov. Podatki zbrani s spletnimi anketami pogosto vključujejo tehnične informacije, kot so uporaba brskalnika, čas anketiranja, respondentov IP naslov.

Uporabimo imenovanja t1, t2 (t=technical information)

CSES Module 3 Data Set Errata

Posted: October 24, 2010

SPSS portable files

For the convenience of users, in recent years the CSES project has been providing SPSS portable (.por) files in its data releases. However, an SPSS portable file is not available in the first advance release of CSES Module 3. This is because variable names in SPSS portable files are limited to eight characters in length, and some CSES Module 3 variables names exceed that limit. Until the CSES Secretariat is able to resolve the issue, SPSS portable files will not be provided in CSES Module 3 releases.

Dokumentacija podatkovne datoteke: opis spremenljivk

Podobna načela veljajo tudi za opis spremenljivk:

- bodite kratki (za dolgotrajno hrambo največ 80 znakov)
- kjer je potrebno, ustrezno označite tip spremenljivke in mersko lestvico (numerična / opisna spremenljivka)
- v opisu omenite št. vprašanja v vprašalniku
spremenljivka 'q11hexw' z opisom 'Q11: hours spent taking physical exercise in a typical week'
- pazimo na dosledno dokumentiranje manjkajočih vrednosti, izogibamo se puščanju praznih polj. Kadar vrednosti niso podane v vprašalniku, priporočamo uporabno standardnih oznak.

99=brez odgovora

98=ne vem

97=se ne nanaša, preskok

95= napaka

-1=zakrita vrednost

Dokumentacija podatkovne datoteke: opis spremenljivk

Pri opisih spremenljivk smo pozorni tudi na uporabo:

- Kodiranje oz. uporabo klasifikacijskih shem, z navedbo bibliografske reference

Npr. Standardna klasifikacija poklicev – seznam kod, za umestitev respondentovega poklica; ISO 3166 - 2 mestna koda za državo

- Kadar imamo v datoteki izvedene spremenljivke, pazimo, da so ustrezno pripravljene in imenovane (*npr. iz leta rojstva so generirane starostne skupine*).
- Enako velja tudi za pripravljeno utež (*npr. utež po spolu*).

Kadar je potrebno, pripravimo in distribuiramo ločen dokument, kjer opišemo posamezna preoblikovanja spremenljivk.

Dokumentacija podatkov – prepisi intervjujev

Kvalitativni podatki / tekstovni dokumenti:

- Ustrezen prepis intervjujev – tekst razdeli na govorce, dodaj minute, izloči medmete, po potrebi zapiši tekst iz govornega jezika / narečja v pravopisni jezik.
- V glavo pripravljenega dokumenta dodaj kratke informacije, kot so datum intervjuja, kraj, ime anketarja, informacije o anketirancu, kontekst.

10.9.2011	Projekt Odprti podatki, INTERVJU_št. 21
ANKETAR: Janez Štebe (JŠ)	
DRUGI PRISOTNI: Sanja Lužar (SL)	
INTERVJUVANEC: D.K. (DK)	
ORGANIZACIJA: XXX	
ZNANSTVENO PODROČJE: vodja XXX	
POLOŽAJ: znanstveni sodelavec	
IZOBRAZBA: uni. dipl. inž. XXX	
LETA DELA: /	
LETO ROJSTVA: /	

7 EU VET - Raziskava o poklicnem izobraževanju v sedmih evropskih državah

The 7EU - VET project – Detailed Methodological Approach to Understanding the VET Education - is **a research study on vocational education and training** which builds on theoretical backgrounds and **secondary analyses** of the existing documentation as well as on national and EU data in order to conduct **quantitative and qualitative studies** and derive empirical results. The project is built upon one of the goals of the Lisbon strategy, which is the promotion and the quality of vocational education and training.

EUVET 12

– [Coding of Master questionnaire](#)

EUVET 12 ([Manual for cleaning and entering data](#))

- splošne informacije
- določanje manjkajočih spremenljivk
- problematika specifičnih vprašanj
- vnos podatkov
- kontrola kvalitete
- čiščenje podatkov
- pregledovanje / iskanje napak.

Rotating modules for ESS Round 8 announced

The ESS ERIC Scientific Advisory Board has selected the two successful modules for ESS Round 8. More...

29 Countries

The 3rd International ESS Conference • 13-15th July 2016 • Lausanne, Switzerland [MORE >>](#)

Methodological Research

The European Social Survey runs a programme of research to support and enhance the methodology that underpins the high standards it pursues in every aspect of survey design, data collection and archiving.

Data and Documentation

Data and documentation can be accessed by round (year), by theme or by country. Data are available for download and online analysis.

ESS Resources

The ESS provides a series of outreach resources designed to increase the use of its data, including ESS Bibliography, Findings, Training Courses and eLearning resources.

ESS6 - integrated file

Edition 2.1

Integrated files and documents

ESS6 - integrated file, edition 2.1

ESS6 - data from Interviewer's questionnaire, edition 2.1

ESS6 - test variables from Supplementary questionnaire, edition 1.0

ESS6 - parents' occupation edition 2.1, all country files and integrated isco file

ESS6 - data from Contact forms, edition 2.0

ESS6 - interview time data, edition 1.1

ESS6 - data from Media claims, edition 4.0

Guide to weighting of ESS data

Useful hints: Combining data files, Renaming variables, Other data formats.

Fieldwork Summary and Deviations

Evropska družboslovna raziskava – Podatkovni protokol

B2. Parents' occupation	
B3. Raw data	
B4. Specifications and deposit of Sample design data files (SDDF)	
B5. Common identifiers in data files	
B6. Checking data.....	
B7. Anonymised data, files 1-4	
B8. Deposit of indirectly identifiable data, files 5 and 6.....	
C. Principles of variable definitions	
C1. Missing values	
C2. Multiple responses and missing values	
C3. Formats.....	
C4. Variable names.....	
C5. Variable labels and categories	
D. Standards and classifications	
D1. International standards.....	
D1.1 ISO 3166-1, Country.....	
D1.2 ISO 639-2, Language	

http://www.europeansocialsurvey.org/docs/round6/survey/ESS6_data_protocol_e01_4.pdf

Your Dataset Deserves More than a First Row Header

The screenshot shows the Microsoft Excel interface with the Colectica add-in. The main window displays a dataset of 1978 automobiles. The 'foreign' variable is highlighted in the first row of the data table. The Colectica 'Data Documentation' panel is open on the right, showing the details for the 'foreign' variable, including its label, description, and data type.

	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	
1	headroom	trunk	weight	length	turn	displace	gear_ratio	foreign	
2		2.5	11	2930	186	40	121	3.58	0
3		3	11	3350	173	40	258	2.53	0
4		3	12	2640	168	35	121	3.08	0
5		4.5	16	3250	196	40	196	2.93	0
6		4	20	4080	222	43	350	2.41	0
7		4	21	3670	218	43	231	2.73	0
8		3	10	2230	170	34	304	2.87	0
9		2	16	3280	200	42	196	2.93	0
10		3.5	17	3880	207	43	231	2.93	0
11		3.5	13	3400	200	42	231	3.08	0
12		4	20	4330	221	44	425	2.28	0
13		3.5	16	3900	204	43	350	2.19	0
14		3	13	4290	204	45	350	2.24	0
15		2.5	9	2110	163	34	231	2.93	0
16		4	20	3690	212	43	250	2.56	0
17		3.5	17	3180	193	31	200	2.73	0
18		2	16	3220	200	41	200	2.73	0
19		2	7	2750	179	40	151	2.73	0
20		3.5	13	3430	197	43	250	2.56	0

Data Documentation

Dataset Details | Variable Details | Code List | ⚙️

foreign

Label
Car type

Description
Indicates whether the car was manufactured in the United States or a different country.

Data Type
Code

origin Codes | Update Codes from Data | Use Existing Code List

Additivity
Stack

Colectica for Excel

Document Variables and Datasets

Colectica allows documenting of Variables, Code Lists, and Data Sets directly from within Microsoft Excel.

Import Stata to Excel

Colectica for Excel Professional allows direct importing and documenting of Stata data files, with a file extension .dta. The variable names, labels and code lists in the Stata file will also be imported and added to the stored documentation automatically.

Metadata is Embedded

Colectica saves your standards-based metadata directly in the Microsoft Excel file. If you email or share your file, the metadata will still be attached.

Import SPSS to Excel

Colectica for Excel Professional allows direct importing and documenting of SPSS data files, with a file extension .sav. The variable names, labels and code lists in the SPSS file will also be imported and added to the stored documentation automatically.

Publish Documentation

Colectica for Excel can generate documentation for your Variables, Code Lists, and dataset in PDF, Word, HTML, and XSL-FO.

Create DDI-Lifecycle Metadata

Export your data documentation to an XML file in the DDI metadata format, the standard for data documentation. Open and edit it from Colectica Designer, Colectica Express, or other DDI applications.

Data Documentation

Dataset Details Variable Details Code List Progress

SPSS Import
Reading Data from 17627 rows.

Dataset Details Variable Details Code List

B4_3

Label
My programme provides useful practical experience

Description

Data Type
Code

not answered, not applicable, Not at all Codes

not answered, not applicable, Not at all Codes

Update Codes from Data Use Existing Code List

Additivity
Unspecified

Measurement Unit

Data Documentation

Dataset Details Variable Details Code List

not answered, not applicable, Not at all Codes

-88	not answered	x
-77	not applicable	x
1	Not at all	x
2	Slightly	x
3	Fairly	x
4	Quite	x
5	Completely	x

Microsoft Excel ribbon showing the 'Data Documentation' button highlighted with an orange circle. The ribbon includes FILE, HOME, INSERT, PAGE LAYOUT, FORMULAS, DATA, and COLECTIC. The 'Data Documentation' button is located in the 'DATA' tab, between 'Document Workbook' and 'From SPSS'.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	ID	Age	Gender	Language				
2	1	30	1	1				
3	2	31	2	1				

Data Documentation

Dataset Details | Variable Details | Code List | ⚙️

Refresh Documentation

Column Count
4

Title
Simple Dataset

Subtitle

Alternate Title

Creator

Publisher

	H	I	J	K	L
1	length	turn	displace	gear_ratio	foreign
2	186	40	121	3.58	0
3	173	40	258	2.53	0
4	168	35	121	3.08	0
5	196	40	196	2.93	0
6	222	43	350	2.41	0
7	218	43	231	2.73	0
8	170	34	304	2.87	0
9	200	42	196	2.93	0
10	207	43	231	2.93	0
11	200	42	231	3.08	0
12	221	44	425	2.28	0
13	204	43	350	2.19	0
14	204	45	350	2.24	0
15	163	34	231	2.93	0
16	212	43	250	2.56	0
17	193	31	200	2.73	0
18	200	41	200	2.73	0
19	179	40	151	2.73	0
20	197	43	250	2.56	0

Data Documentation

Dataset Details | Variable Details | Code List | ⚙️

turn

Label
Turn Circle (ft.)

Description
The turning circle of a vehicle is the size of the smallest circular turn (i.e. U-turn) that the vehicle capable of making.

Data Type
Numeric

Type
Integer

Nesstar Publisher

Nesstar Publisher – okolje, v katerem lahko urejamo podatke iz različnih virov (vključujoč SPSS, SAS, Excel itd.).

Orodje ponuja prilagojen metapodatkovni urejevalnik, možnost preverjanja kvalitete podatkov in metapodatkov, ter metapodatkovno podlago, ki omogoča standardizacijo in kontrolo nad vnosom.

Easy editing/creation and export of DDI documented datasets with XML experience needed.

Tools to compute/recode/label new, or existing, variables to be added to a dataset before publishing.

Tools to validate metadata and variables.

The ability to import and export data to the most common statistical formats, including delimited files.

The ability to include automatically generated frequency and summary statistics for each variable.

Multilingual - Arabic, Chinese, English, French, Portuguese, Russian and Spanish and more.

Podatkovni formati, ki jih podpira Nesstar Publisher

File formats currently supported:

- Nesstar (.Nesstar)
- NSDstat (.NSDstat)
- DDI Document (*.xml)
- SPSS (*.sav)
- SPSS Portable (*.por)
- SPSS Syntax (*.sps)
- STATA (*.dta)
- Statistica (*.sta)
- NSDstat (*.nsf),
- dBase (*.dbf)
- DIF (*.dif)
- Delimited Text (*.txt, *.csv, *.sdv, *.cdv, *.prn)
- PC-Axis (*.px)
- Excel (*.xls)
- Hierarchy Definition File (*.NSDstatHDef)

File size limitations: The maximum size of file that can be imported is approximately 10 Gigabytes, with a limitation within a file to 260 million cases. However, using files of this size will affect response times.

Projects:

- My Projects
 - euvet12-en_F1
 - Document Description
 - Study Description
 - Other Study Materials
 - Datasets
 - euvet12-en_F1
 - Key Variables & Relations
 - Variables
 - Data Entry**
 - Cell Notes
 - Cube Setups
 - Variable Groups
 - Other Materials
 - External Resources

Data Entry

	v1 - Country	v2 - ScholD	v3 - Class	v4 - StudenID	v5 - A1_Aus	v6 - A1_Gre	v7 - A1_Lat	v8 - a1_la0	v9 - a1_la1	v10
1	Slovenia	5111	not answer	51113011	not applicabl	not applicabl	-77			
2	Slovenia	5111	not answer	51113012	not applicabl	not applicabl	-77			
3	Lithuania	1001	Class One	1001012098	not applicabl	not applicabl	-77			
4	Lithuania	1001	Class One	1001012099	not applicabl	not applicabl	-77			
5	Lithuania	1001	Class One	1001012100	not applicabl	not applicabl	-77			
6	Lithuania	1001	Class One	1001012103	not applicabl	not applicabl	-77			
7	Lithuania	1001	Class One	1001012270	not applicabl	not applicabl	-77			
8	Lithuania	1001	Class One	1001012271	not applicabl	not applicabl	-77			
9	Lithuania	1001	Class One	1001012272	not applicabl	not applicabl	-77			
10	Lithuania	1001	Class One	1001012562	not applicabl	not applicabl	-77			
11	Lithuania	1001	Class One	1001012575	not applicabl	not applicabl	-77			
12	Lithuania	1001	Class One	1001012593	not applicabl	not applicabl	-77			
13	Lithuania	1001	Class Two	1001021072	not applicabl	not applicabl	-77			
14	Lithuania	1001	Class Two	1001021124	not applicabl	not applicabl	-77			
15	Lithuania	1001	Class Two	1001021125	not applicabl	not applicabl	-77			
16	Lithuania	1001	Class Two	1001021126	not applicabl	not applicabl	-77			
17	Lithuania	1001	Class Two	1001021127	not applicabl	not applicabl	-77			
18	Lithuania	1001	Class Two	1001021130	not applicabl	not applicabl	-77			
19	Lithuania	1001	Class Two	1001021132	not applicabl	not applicabl	-77			

My Projects

- euvet12-en_F1
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 - euvet12-en_F1
 - Key Variables & Relations
 - Variables**
 - Data Entry
 - Cell Notes
 - Cube Setups
 - Variable Groups
 - Other Materials
 - External Resources

Variables

Number	Name	Label
v63	B2a_ISCO	ISCO: What is the title of the programme you are enrolled on?
v64	B2b	What is the total duration of this programme? (In years)
v65	B2c	In what year of your programme are you in?
v66	B3_1	How many school hours per week do you spend at school?
v67	B3_2	I attend block release.
v68	B4_1	My programme ensures employment in the job market.
v69	B4_2	My programme enables me to receive a good starting salary/wage when I graduate.
v70	B4_3	My programme provides useful practical experience for entering the workforce.
v71	B4_4	My programme offers me a broad perspective for a professional career.
v72	B4_5	My programme prepares me well for further education and training.
v73	B4_6	My programme prepares me for starting my own business or becoming an employer.

Documentation

Statistics

- Include Weighted Statistics
- Include Frequencies
- List Missing At End

Sorting of Frequencies:

Value (ascending)

Summary Statistics Options:

- Include Valid
- Include Min
- Include Max
- Include Mean
- Include Weighted Mean
- Include StdDev
- Include Weighted StdDev

Category Hierarchy

- 77 - not applicable
- 1 - Not at all
- 2 - Slightly

Value: Label:

Category Text:

Level Name:

GeoMap URI:

Variable information

Data Type: Numeric

Measure: Nominal

- Is Time Variable
- Is Weight Variable

Min: -77 Max: 5 Decimals: 0

- Implicit decimals

Missing data:

= -88

*

Variables

Number	Name	Label	Width	StartCol	EndCol	Record	Dec
v63	B2a_ISCO	ISCO: What is the title of the programme you are enrolled on?	8	*	*	*	
v64	B2b	What is the total duration of this programme? (In years)	11	*	*	*	
v65	B2c	In what year of your programme are you in?	11	*	*	*	
v66	B3_1	How many school hours per week do you spend at school?	11	*	*	*	
v67	B3_2	I attend block release.	11	*	*	*	
v68	B4_1	My programme ensures employment in the job market.	11	*	*	*	
v69	B4_2	My programme enables me to receive a good starting salary/wage when su	11	*	*	*	
v70	B4_3	My programme provides useful practical experience for entering the workf	11	*	*	*	
v71	B4_4	My programme offers me a broad perspective for a professional career.	11	*	*	*	
v72	B4_5	My programme prepares me well for further education and training.	11	*	*	*	
v73	B4_6	My programme prepares me for starting my own business or becoming self	11	*	*	*	
v74	B4_7	My programme is recognised within society as having a good reputation.	11	*	*	*	
v75	B4_8	My programme prepares me for a job that is important for society.	11	*	*	*	
v76	B5_1	Satisfaction: Most of my classes are interesting.	11	*	*	*	
v77	B5_2	Satisfaction: Most of my teachers are usually well prepared when teaching	11	*	*	*	

- [-] Category Hierarchy
- [-] -77 - not applicable
- [-] 1 - Not at all
- [+] 2 - Slightly
- [-] 3 - Fairly
- [-] 4 - Quite
- [-] 5 - Completely
- [-] -88 - not answered

+
-
↑
↓
↔

Value: Label:

Category Text:

Level Name:

GeoMap URI:

▼ Variable information

Data Type:

Measure:

Data Type:

Measure:

Is Time Variable

Is Weight Variable

Min: Max: Decimals:

Implicit decimals

Missing data:

<input type="text" value="="/>	<input type="text" value="-88"/>	<input style="width: 90%;" type="text"/>
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text" value="*"/>	<input style="width: 90%;" type="text"/>
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input style="width: 90%;" type="text"/>

▼ Documentation

Statistics

Weights

Documentation

- Include Weighted Statistics
- Include Frequencies
- List Missing At End

Sorting of Frequencies:

Value (ascending)

Summary Statistics Options:

- Include Valid
- Include Min
- Include Max
- Include Mean
- Include Weighted Mean
- Include StdDev
- Include Weighted StdDev

Frequencies:

Value	Label	N	
-77	not applicable	0	0%
1	Not at all	523	3%
2	Slightly	1753	10.1%
3	Fairly	4811	27.7%
4	Quite	6218	35.9%
5	Completely	4036	23.3%
-88	not answered	286	Missing

Summary Statistics:

Type	Value
Valid	17341
Mean	3.663

Variable Groups

- Variable Groups
 - A_F1: Preliminary program and the tra
 - B_F1: Current programme
 - C_F1: Acquired Knowledge
 - D_F1: About yourself and your career**
 - E_F1: Acquired skills and abilities
 - F_F1: Information and communication
 - G_F1: You and your family
 - Other_F1
 - A_F2: Preliminary program and the tra
 - B_F2: Current programme
 - C_F2: Acquired Knowledge
 - D_F2: About yourself and your career
 - E_F2: Acquired skills and abilities
 - F_F2: Information and communication
 - G_F2: You and your family
 - Other_F2

+		Description	Variables			
-	↑	↓	Dataset	Number	Name	Label
			euvet12_f1	v148	D1_1	Goals: Obtaining solid occupational proficiencies
			euvet12_f1	v149	D1_2	Goals: Receiving a high income
			euvet12_f1	v150	D1_3	Goals: Gaining job security
			euvet12_f1	v151	D1_4	Goals: Having responsibility at work
			euvet12_f1	v152	D1_5	Goals: Having opportunities to learn new things at work
			euvet12_f1	v153	D1_6	Goals: Undertaking interesting tasks in the workplace
			euvet12_f1	v154	D1_7	Goals: Having a job that makes me happy
			euvet12_f1	v155	D1_8	Goals: Having a good relationship with colleagues
			euvet12_f1	v156	D1_9	Goals: Advancing to a high level of status in society
			euvet12_f1	v157	D1_10	Goals: having enough spare-time to do other things in life
			euvet12_f1	v158	D1_11	Goals: Making and maintaining relationships with others (e.g. family and friends)
			euvet12_f1	v159	D2_1	Role: A woman should be prepared to cut down on her paid work for the sake of her family (not asked
			euvet12_f1	v160	D2_2	Role: When jobs are scarce, men should have more right to a job than women (not asked in UK)
			euvet12_f1	v161	D2_3	Role: There should be many more women in political and public leadership roles (not asked in UK)
			euvet12_f1	v162	D2_4	Role: Men should take as much responsibility as women for the home and children (not asked in UK)
			euvet12_f1	v163	D2_5	Role: A man who stays at home and runs the household is not a real man (not asked in UK)
			euvet12_f1	v164	D2_6	Role: When there are children in the home, parents should stay together even if they do not get along
			euvet12_f1	v165	D2_7	Role: A persons family ought to be his or her main priority in life (not asked in UK)
			euvet12_f1	v166	D3	Do you think men and women have the same opportunities to get a job in your aspired occupation? (n
			euvet12_f1	v167	D4	What kind of job do you expect to have when you are about 30 years old?
			euvet12_f1	v168	d40	What kind of job do you expect to have when you are about 30 years old?
			euvet12_f1	v169	d41	What kind of job do you expect to have when you are about 30 years old?
			euvet12_f1	v170	d42	What kind of job do you expect to have when you are about 30 years old?
			euvet12_f1	v171	D4_ISCO	ISCO: What kind of job do you expect to have when you are about 30 years old?
			euvet12_f1	v172	D5_1	Sector: Industry (e.g. producing industry, steel, motor, oil)
			euvet12_f1	v173	D5_2	Sector: Services (e.g. nursing, policing, hairdressing)

v31	A3_3a_2	Previous grade: first foreign language_comparable	8	*	*	1
v32	A4_1	Choice: The programme offered good job prospects	11	*	*	1
v33	A4_2	Choice: My previous examination grades prevented me being able to enrol	11	*	*	1
v34	A4_3	Choice: My parents suggested I enrol on this programme	11	*	*	1

▼ Documentation

Statistics

Weights

Documentation

Question

- Pre-Question Text
- Literal Question
- Post-Question Text
- Interviewer Instructions

Description

- Variable Text
- Concepts

Literal Question

A4. How important were the following aspects to you when you were choosing your current programme? (Please tick only one box in each row) The programme offered good job prospects

Dokumentacija

Dokumentacija vključuje:

- anketni vprašalnik,
- popis ozadja intervjujev,
- informacije o respondentih in njihove demografske značilnosti (zlasti v kvalitativnih raziskavah),
- tabelo imen in opisov spremenljivk,
- članek, ki nudi dodatne informacije o raziskovanju,
- opis metodologije uporabljene pri zbiranju podatkov.

Nashville, Tennessee Music Industry Economic Impact Project

The Nashville Chamber of Commerce, in conjunction with the Music City Partnership and Belmont University, is conducting an economic impact study of the music industry in Nashville, Tennessee. This survey questionnaire is part of that study. The information received on this questionnaire will be held in strict confidence and no specific firm information will be released or published. In addition, all questionnaires and firm-specific information will be destroyed once the study is completed. If you have any questions, please contact Dr. Patrick Raine of Belmont University at 615-460-6175. Please return this survey by October 24, 2005. A stamped envelope is enclosed for your convenience.

Company Name _____
Contact Person _____
Telephone # _____ Fax # _____
Please specify primary nature of business _____

	Past Fiscal Yr.	Estimated Current Fiscal Yr.
Labor		
Total Number of Full-time Employees (Nashville, MSA) ^a	_____	_____
Total Number of Part-time Employees (Nashville, MSA)	_____	_____
Annual Employee Wages and Salaries	_____	_____
Professional/ Business Services, contract and additional labor	_____	_____
Operations		
Total Operating Expenditures ^b	_____	_____
Capital Improvements		
Total Capital Expenditures	_____	_____
Projected 3-Year Capital Expenditures	_____	_____
Taxes		
State Taxes	_____	_____
Local Taxes	_____	_____
Total Nashville Sales Revenues ^c	_____	_____

Quality report

Kaj naj bo ohranjeno?

Kontekstualne informacije o projektu in podatkih

- ozadje, zgodovina projekta, nameni in cilji raziskave, hipoteze
- publikacije, ki temeljijo na zbranih podatkih

Metodologija in procesiranje podatkovne zbirke

- vzorčenje in proces zbiranja podatkov
- uporabljen inštrument – vprašalniki, pokazne kartice, zapiski anketarja o anketiranjih
- geografsko pokritje
- preverjanje podatkov – čiščenje, preverjanje napak
- izvedba / izračun izvedenih spremenljivk
- uteževanje: spremenljivke, proces uteževanja
- uporabljeni sekundarni viri

Zaupnost podatkov, dostop in pogoji uporabne

- izvedeni postopki anonimizacije
- privolitev - pogoji / postopki
- pogoji dostopa in uporabe podatkov

Osnovna struktura DDI 2.*

- Metapodatki – podatki o podatkih / standardi
 - Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) Multilingual XML
 - ISO19115
 - Dublin Core
 - Metadata Encoding and Transmission Standard (METS)
 - Preservation Metadata Maintenance Activity (PREMIS)

Controlled Vocabulary

Semantic and technical **interoperability**

- Section 1.0 - **Opis dokumenta** (Document Description) consists of bibliographic information that can be considered as the header whose elements uniquely describe the full contents of the compliant DDI file.
- Section 2.0 - **Opis raziskave** (Study Description) consists of information about the data collection. This section includes information about who collected and who distributes the data, about the scope and coverage, sampling (if relevant), data collection methods and processing, citation requirements, etc.

Osnovna struktura DDI 2.*

Section 3.0 - **Opis podatkovne datoteke** (Data Files Description) provides information about the Data file(s).

Section 4.0 - **Opis spremenljivk** (Variable Description) provides a detailed description of variables, including (when relevant) the variable type, variable and value labels, literal questions, computation or imputation methods, instructions to interviewers, universe, descriptive statistics, etc.

Section 5.0 - **Povezana gradiva** (Other Study Related Materials) allows for the inclusion of other materials related to the study such as questionnaires, user manuals, computer programs, interviewer manuals, maps, coding information, etc.

Datotečni sistem

Skrbim za urejenost map in smiselno poimenovanje.

EUVET 12 Raziskava

7EU_VET	Today 08:43	--	Folder
▶ survey	Yesterday 09:44	--	Folder
▶ tabele_za_net	18 Oct 2012 11:46	--	Folder
▶ focus groups	18 Oct 2012 11:45	--	Folder
▶ opisRaziskave.docx	9 Oct 2012 12:20	113 KB	Micros...ument
▶ wp_ji	5 Jun 2012 09:45	--	Folder
▶ questionnaires_final	5 Jun 2012 09:45	--	Folder
▶ vet docuementnts	5 Jun 2012 09:45	--	Folder
▶ tuja praksa	5 Jun 2012 09:45	--	Folder
▶ tasks	5 Jun 2012 09:45	--	Folder
▶ samo_draft material	5 Jun 2012 09:41	--	Folder
▶ data	5 Jun 2012 09:41	--	Folder
▶ samo-minutes	5 Jun 2012 09:41	--	Folder
▶ presentations	5 Jun 2012 09:41	--	Folder
▶ logoti	5 Jun 2012 09:41	--	Folder
▶ manuals	5 Jun 2012 09:41	--	Folder
▶ finalni	5 Jun 2012 09:41	--	Folder
▶ gantt chart	5 Jun 2012 09:41	--	Folder
▶ documentation	5 Jun 2012 09:41	--	Folder
▶ baza_poklicne	5 Jun 2012 09:41	--	Folder
▶ baze	5 Jun 2012 09:41	--	Folder
▶ baza_gimn	5 Jun 2012 09:41	--	Folder
▶ 7EU-VET budget	5 Jun 2012 09:41	--	Folder
▶ 4th meeting	5 Jun 2012 09:41	--	Folder
▶ 3rd_meeting	5 Jun 2012 09:41	--	Folder
▶ 3rd interim report	5 Jun 2012 09:41	--	Folder
▶ 2nd_interim_repoort	5 Jun 2012 09:41	--	Folder
▶ 2nd meeting	5 Jun 2012 09:41	--	Folder
▶ 1_st_meeting	5 Jun 2012 09:41	--	Folder

Forum: 7EU VET		Threads	Replies	Last post	
	INTERIM REPORT	13	94	ana	Re: WP10 deliverables 04.07.2011 16:32
	WP10 National Reports	7	19	bozidar	Re: National report - Slovenia 13.12.2012 11:57
	WP1 - Management	6	17	vasja	Draft agenda 4th meeting 23.11.2011 14:48
	WP2 - Quality assurance	9	20	ana	Dehems QA 25.05.2011 15:09
	WP3 - Dissemination	28	93	simon	Re: WP3 Germany 26.11.2012 12:04
	WP4_WP5 Second stage	14	74	vjaceslavs	Re: WP4/5 Latvia 17.03.2012 22:40
	WP4 - An overview of existing documentation	8	26	Markos	Re: WP4 - Latest Version 28.06.2010 19:51
	WP5 - Secondary study of national contexts and trends	6	55	simon	WP5: Updated Report 2012 04.12.2012 13:23
	WP6 - Focus groups with pupils of secondary school	6	62	barbara	Re: Focus Groups - second round... 24.10.2012 12:31
	WP7 - Survey among secondary school pupils	45	294	barbara	primerjava gimnazije poklicne 20.07.2012 11:26
	WP8 - Qualitative interviews among experts and decision makers	5	25	simon	WP8: 2nd draft of Int. Report 19.11.2012 13:22
	WP9 - Exploitation of results	7	27	virginija	Re: National exploitation-Lithuania... 14.01.2013 08:24
	WP10 - Synthesis of the results	8	15	bozidar	Final report - draft version1.... 07.12.2012 13:36
	Other	11	50	caroline	Progress report submitted 30.06.2011 11:55
	Zapisniki - Irena	4	6	tinad	Zapisnik sestanka z dne 23.2.2011... 24.02.2011 09:21
	Meetings	12	25	andrejap	IISES 2012, Lisbon 05.11.2012 10:23
	Zapisniki VV; BB, SP	27	126	gc	SUBMISSION 04.03.2013 09:50
	Admin	6	7	vasja	Re: Amendment request JUNIJ 2011... 08.06.2011 10:42
	FINAL REPORT	13	28	bozidar	Re: WP8 deliverables 23.01.2013 11:48
Forum: Special forums		Threads	Replies	Last post	
	last threads				

[Add thread](#)

- **Forum: 7EU VET**
- INTERIM REPORT
- WP10 National Reports
- WP1 - Management
- WP2 - Quality assurance
- WP3 - Dissemination
- WP4_WP5 Second stage
- WP4 - An overview of existing documentation
- WP5 - Secondary study of national contexts and trends
- WP6 - Focus groups with pupils of secondary school
- WP7 - Survey among secondary school pupils
- WP8 - Qualitative interviews among experts and decision makers
- WP9 - Exploitation of results
- WP10 - Synthesis of the results
- Other
- Zapisniki - Irena
- Meetings
- Zapisniki VV; BB, SP
- Admin
- [FINAL REPORT](#)
- Forum: Special forums**
- last threads

Folder: FINAL REPORT	Replies	Views	Author	Last post
WP8 deliverables	2	34	barbara	23.01.2013 11:48 - bozidar
WP6 deliverables	2	23	barbara	23.01.2013 11:47 - bozidar
WP7 deliverables	3	55	barbara	23.01.2013 11:47 - bozidar
WP5 deliverables	2	21	barbara	23.01.2013 11:45 - bozidar
WP4 deliverables	2	29	barbara	23.01.2013 11:45 - bozidar
WP1 deliverables	4	96	barbara	23.01.2013 11:44 - bozidar
WP3 deliverables	3	60	barbara	23.01.2013 11:44 - bozidar
WP2 deliverables	2	33	barbara	23.01.2013 11:44 - bozidar
WP10 deliverables	2	110	barbara	05.11.2012 07:18 - julian
WORKPLAN scheldlue	3	64	vasja	27.06.2012 13:18 - vasja
DELIVRALBE LIST	1	44	vasja	11.11.2011 13:49 - vasja
WP9 deliverables	1	35	barbara	19.10.2011 09:59 - barbara
Final report plan	1	57	barbara	19.10.2011 09:51 - barbara

7.4 International database

One of the WP 7 products will be a **publicly accessible international database** with the corresponding documentation (questionnaires, technical information, sampling information) based on which anyone interested will be able to perform secondary analyses. The international database will be published on the web page and publicly after the publication of the final report.

Nesstar Publisher

Projects:

- My Projects
 - euvet12-en_F1
 - euvet12-en
 - Document Description
 - Study Description
 - Other Study Materials
 - Datasets
 - Variable Groups
 - Other Materials
 - External Resources

Other Materials

- 7 EU VET – Study on vocational ed
- 7 EU VET – Berufsbildungssysteme
- 7 EU VET – Raziskava o poklicnem i
- 7 EU VET – Raziskava o poklicnem i
- 7 EU - Berufsschüler in Europa - Ge
- 7 EU VET – Detalizeta metodologisk
- 7 EU VET – Septyniū Europos šaliu
- 7 EU VET – Detailed Methodologica
- 7EU VET Coding for Master Questio
- 7EU VET Coding of answer categor
- Manual for Entering and Cleaning [
- Sample design

Title:
7 EU - Berufsschüler in Europa - German [Questionnaire]

Location (URI):
http://www.7eu-vet.org/uploadi/editor/1309423056pupil_DE.pdf

Description:

Other Materials

- 7 EU VET – Study on vocational ed
- 7 EU VET – Berufsbildungssysteme
- 7 EU VET – Raziskava o poklicnem i
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- 7 EU VET – Detailed Methodologica
- 7EU VET Coding for Master Questio
- 7EU VET Coding of answer categor
- Manual for Entering and Cleaning [
- Sample design

Title:
7 EU VET – Study on vocational education in seven european countries [Questionnaire]

Location (URI):
http://www.7eu-vet.org/db/18/833/Project%20results/Questionnaires_WP7/

Description:

Study Description

Title

[EUVET12]3 7 EU VET - Study on vocational education in seven european countries

Authoring Entity / Primary Investigator

Name	Affiliation
Dahmen, Caroline	University of Damstadt, Germany
Brečko, Barbara	Fakulteta za družbene vede = Faculty of Social Sciences, Univerza v Ljubljani = University of Ljubljana, Slovenia
Fuchs, Marek	University of Damstadt, Germany
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Distributors

Name	Abbreviation	Affiliation
Arhiv družboslovnih podatkov = Social Science Data Archives	ADP	Univerza v Ljubljani = University of Ljubljana

Producers

Name	Abbreviation	Affiliation
Center za družboslovno informatiko = Centre for Social Informatics	CDI	Fakulteta za družbene vede = Faculty of Social Sc

Fundings

Agency	Grant Number
The European Commission-Life long Learning programme (75 %)	2009-12029
Own resources of the participating institutions (25 %)	2009-12029

Keywords

Text
vocational education
vocational programme
knowledge
competences

Variable Groups

- Variable Groups
 - A_F1: Preliminary program and the tra
 - B_F1: Current programme
 - C_F1: Acquired Knowledge
 - D_F1: About yourself and your career**
 - E_F1: Acquired skills and abilities
 - F_F1: Information and communication
 - G_F1: You and your family
 - Other_F1
 - A_F2: Preliminary program and the tra
 - B_F2: Current programme
 - C_F2: Acquired Knowledge
 - D_F2: About yourself and your career
 - E_F2: Acquired skills and abilities
 - F_F2: Information and communication
 - G_F2: You and your family
 - Other_F2

Description		Variables	
Dataset	Number	Name	Label
euvet12_f1	v148	D1_1	Goals: Obtaining solid occupational proficiencies
euvet12_f1	v149	D1_2	Goals: Receiving a high income
euvet12_f1	v150	D1_3	Goals: Gaining job security
euvet12_f1	v151	D1_4	Goals: Having responsibility at work
euvet12_f1	v152	D1_5	Goals: Having opportunities to learn new things at work
euvet12_f1	v153	D1_6	Goals: Undertaking interesting tasks in the workplace
euvet12_f1	v154	D1_7	Goals: Having a job that makes me happy
euvet12_f1	v155	D1_8	Goals: Having a good relationship with colleagues
euvet12_f1	v156	D1_9	Goals: Advancing to a high level of status in society
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euvet12_f1	v158	D1_11	Goals: Making and maintaining relationships with others (e.g. family and friends)
euvet12_f1	v159	D2_1	Role: A woman should be prepared to cut down on her paid work for the sake of her family (not asked
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euvet12_f1	v161	D2_3	Role: There should be many more women in political and public leadership roles (not asked in UK)
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euvet12_f1	v164	D2_6	Role: When there are children in the home, parents should stay together even if they do not get along
euvet12_f1	v165	D2_7	Role: A persons family ought to be his or her main priority in life (not asked in UK)
euvet12_f1	v166	D3	Do you think men and women have the same opportunities to get a job in your aspired occupation? (n
euvet12_f1	v167	D4	What kind of job do you expect to have when you are about 30 years old?
euvet12_f1	v168	d40	What kind of job do you expect to have when you are about 30 years old?
euvet12_f1	v169	d41	What kind of job do you expect to have when you are about 30 years old?
euvet12_f1	v170	d42	What kind of job do you expect to have when you are about 30 years old?
euvet12_f1	v171	D4_ISCO	ISCO: What kind of job do you expect to have when you are about 30 years old?
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euvet12_f1	v173	D5_2	Sector: Services (e.g. nursing, policing, hairdressing)

v31	A3_3a_2	Previous grade: first foreign language_comparable	8	*	*	1
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v33	A4_2	Choice: My previous examination grades prevented me being able to enrol	11	*	*	1
v34	A4_3	Choice: My parents suggested I enrol on this programme	11	*	*	1

▼ Documentation

Statistics | Weights | Documentation

- Question
 - Pre-Question Text
 - Literal Question
 - Post-Question Text
 - Interviewer Instructions
- Description
 - Variable Text
 - Concepts

Literal Question

A4. How important were the following aspects to you when you were choosing your current programme? (Please tick only one box in each row) The programme offered good job prospects

Survey Documentation

ESS6 Data Documentation Report ed. 2.1

ESS6 Appendix A1 Education ed. 2.0

[European Social Survey, Round 6](#)

ESS6 Appendix A2 Income ed. 2.0

ESS6 Appendix A3 Political Parties ed. 2.0

ESS6 Appendix A4 Legal Marital and Relationship Status ed. 2.0

ESS6 Appendix A5 Population Statistics ed. 2.0

ESS6 Appendix A6 Classifications and Coding Standards

ESS6 Appendix A7 Variables and Questions ed. 2.1

ESS6 Appendix A8 Variable List ed. 2.1

ESS6 Data Protocol ed. 1.4

ESS6 Quality Report

Fieldwork Documents

ESS6 Source Main Questionnaire

ESS6 Source Showcards Main Questionnaire

ESS6 Source Contact Forms

ESS6 Source Supplementary Questionnaires

ESS6 Source Showcards Supplementary Questionnaires

ESS6 Source Administration of Supplementary Questionnaires

ESS6 Source Project Instructions

Reference

FSD – Data Management Guidelines

<http://www.fsd.uta.fi/aineistonhallinta/en/>

UKDA – Create & Manage Data

<http://www.data-archive.ac.uk/create-manage>

ICSPR – Guide to Social Science Data Preparation and Archiving

<http://www.icpsr.umich.edu/icpsrweb/content/deposit/guide/chapter5.html>

IHSN – Data archiving and dissemination

<http://www.ihsn.org/home/archiving>

MANTRA – Research Data Management Training

<http://datalib.edina.ac.uk/mantra/>

Kontakt

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